

Holy wood

Furniture valorising locally recovered waste wood

In a micro-value chain approach, old furniture and solid wood pieces are collected locally, dismantled and recovered so that it can be reused in new furniture. A cooperative association of designers and joiners creates a brand for unique, designed furniture pieces, appreciated by clients for their authentic touch of recycled wooden material.

Highlights of innovative features

- An abundant waste stream becomes a raw material for valuable products: The furniture is made by 85-100% of recovered wood!
- The furniture is handmade and created either in small series or as single projects corresponding to the clients' needs, giving them an individual, personalized character.
- The association supports solidarity as the old furniture is obtained mainly from the Emmaüs social cooperative that acts against poverty and exclusion.

Old wooden furniture that cannot be sold any more and would otherwise be incinerated is coming to a second life and re-circulated to local use. Upcycling of old furniture into individual furniture pieces for private homes, offices and public cultural spaces helps to create awareness for local raw material collection and valorization.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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